

Synthesis of Isoquinolines : A Rearrangement in Pictet-Gam's Reaction*

N. L. Dutta, M. S. Wadia† and A. P. Bindra‡

Pictet-Gam's cyclisation of the amide (VII) has been conclusively shown to yield the rearranged product (VI) and not the expected compound (V). Similar aryl migrations have also been shown to occur with three other amides (XII), (XX) and (XXIV).

The cyclodehydration of β -hydroxy β -phenethyl amides (I), to directly furnish isoquinolines (II), constitutes the well studied Pictet-Gam's (PG) reaction¹⁻³. The corresponding methoxy amides (III) have also⁴ been used as starting materials, the choice between the two methods depending on the availability of intermediates. It has been demonstrated⁵⁻⁷ that removal of water from the ethyl amide side chain precedes cyclisation, as shown by the isolation in certain cases of the substituted vinyl amides (IV). UV studies have established⁸⁻⁹ that the same sequence of reactions is involved in the cyclisation of hydroxy amides having activating groups in the benzene ring.

Though the PG reaction has been extensively studied³ no rearrangement during this reaction has so far been reported. It was therefore quite surprising that the known Pictet-Gam's synthesis of 1-methyl-3-phenyl isoquinoline (V) should afford a product now clearly shown to be 1-methyl-4-phenyl isoquinoline (VI). This rearrangement and its extension to substituted compounds is discussed in the present communication.

In the course of our work¹¹⁻¹² on the synthesis of some alkaloids of the berberine group it became necessary to prepare 1-methyl-3-phenyl isoquinoline (V). One of the known methods¹⁰ for preparing this compound used the Pictet-Gam's cyclisation of the erythro hydroxy amide (VII). The gummy product isolated by these workers¹⁰, characterised as the picrate m.p. 218°, was presumed to be 1-methyl-3-phenyl isoquinoline. By following the

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†Present address : University of Poona, Poona-7.

‡Present address : Australian National University, Dept. of Chemistry, Canberra. Australia.

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3. W. M. Whaley and T. R. Govindachari. *Org. Reactions*. John Wiley and Sons, Inc. New York, **6**, 76.
4. K. W. Rosemund, M. Nothnagel and H. Russenfeldt, *Ber.*, 1927, **60**, 392.
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9. E. Uarga and G. Fodar, *J. Pract. Chem.*, 1938, **150**, 94.
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12. A. A. Bindra, M. S. Wadia and N. L. Dutta, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, **7**, 744.

same procedure we have now isolated a crystalline compound, $C_{16}H_{13}N$, m.p. 79° , picrate m.p. 225° . Other methods^{13,14} for the preparation of this compound have been reported to furnish a product m.p. $48-49^\circ$, picrate m.p. $204-205^\circ$ ¹³, $199-200^\circ$ ¹⁴. An unambiguous synthesis of 1-methyl-3-phenyl isoquinoline was then accomplished by treatment of the known¹⁵ pyrrilium salt (VIII) with ammonia followed by dehydrogenation. The UV (Table 1) and NMR (Table 2) of the product, $C_{16}H_{13}N$, m.p. 48° , picrate m.p. $202-04^\circ$, thus obtained were

TABLE 1

UV Spectra of 3 and 4 Aryl Isoquinolines.

3-Aryl	λ m/ μ (log ϵ)
1-Methyl-3- Phenyl (V)	245 (4.69) ; 288 (3.15)
1-Methyl-6, 7 methylenedioxy-3 phenyl (XVI)	233 (4.59) ; 250 (sh)* ; 260 (sh) ; 290 (sh)
1-Methyl, 6, 7 methylenedioxy-3 (3, 4 methylenedioxy phenyl)(XXV)	214 (4.29) ; 236 (4.41) ; 294 (3.76) ; 366(3.64)
4-Aryl	
Isoquinoline ¹⁶	215 (4.91) ; 263 (3.52) ; 306 (3.32) ; 320(3.34)
1-Methyl 4-Phenyl (VI)	221 (4.66) ; 274(3.62) ; 312(3.54)
4-Phenyl (XIII)	218 (4.72), 276 (3.54) ; 310 (3.44)
1-Methyl 6, 7 Methylenedioxy-4-Phenyl (XVII)	219 (4.49) ; 257(4.77) ; 288 (sh) ; 340 (sh)
1-Methyl-6, 7 Methylenedioxy-4-(3, 4 methylene- dioxy phenyl) (XXVI)	235 (4.56) ; 293 (3.95)

*sh = shoulder

TABLE 2

PMR Spectra of 3 and 4 Aryl Isoquinolines.

3-Aryl	Solvent	C_3	C_1	$H^{2'}$ — $H^{6'}$	$H-3'4'5'$	C^1 -Me/H
1-Methyl 3-Phenyl	(V) CCl_4	—	7.66 (s)	8.0 (q) $J = 2, 7.5$ c/s	7.2-7.8 (m)	2.8 (s, 3H)
1-Methyl 6, 7 methylenedioxy- 3-phenyl	(XVI) DMSO	—	7.6 (s)	8.0 (q) $(J = 2, 8$ c/s)	not clear	
1-Methyl 4-Phenyl	(VI) CCl_4	8.25 (s)	—	7.4 (s)	7.4 (s)	2.9 (s, 3H)
4-Phenyl	(XIII) CCl_4	8.33 (s)	—	7.4 (s)	7.4 (s)	9.16 (s, 1H)
1-Methyl-6, 7 methy- lenedioxy-4-Phenyl	(XVII) DMSO	8.15 (s)	—	(assignments not clear)		—
1-Methyl-6, 7 methyle- nedioxy-4 (3, 4 methyle- nedioxy phenyl)	(XXVI) DMSO	8.03(s)	—	$H-6'$ 6.9 (q) $J = 2, 8.5$ c/s $H-2'$ 7.05 (d) $J = 2$ c/s	$H-5'$ 7.075 (d) $J = 7.5$ c/s	—

s = singlet ; d = doublet ; q = quartet ; m = multiplet

13. S. Goszczyński *Roczniki, Chem. Abs.*, 1965, **62**, 16188a.
14. B. Bhattacharya, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, **2**, 25.
15. G. N. Dorofeenko and V. I. Dulenko, *Chem. Abs.*, 1964, **61**, 9458.
16. J. R. Barnard and L. M. Jackman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 1172.

consistent with its formulation as 1-methyl-3-phenyl isoquinoline. The isomeric compound obtained through cyclodehydration must therefore be a rearranged product. As the UV of this product (Table 1) is very similar to that of isoquinoline itself, this compound could be formulated as 1-methyl-4-phenyl isoquinoline. It being expected¹⁷ that the phenyl group at C-4 causes no change in the UV spectrum as it is twisted out of the plane of the isoquinoline nucleus.

The NMR spectrum supported this reasoning. It displayed a low field singlet at 8.25 δ assignable to the C-3 proton.* As this proton appeared as a singlet, it is obvious that C-4 must carry a substituent which can only be the phenyl group which had migrated during the reaction. This argument is further supported by the observation that the NMR spectrum (Table 2) displayed a 5-proton singlet which can only be assigned to the equivalent protons of the phenyl nucleus. These protons are equivalent because the phenyl group, being twisted out of plane, is not conjugated with the isoquinoline system. This feature (5H singlet) is a common feature of 4-phenyl isoquinolines (vide infra) and helps to distinguish these from 3-phenyl isoquinolines in which the 2' and 6' protons appear at lower field (Table 2).

β - β Diphenyl ethyl amine (IX), obtained by reduction of diphenyl acetonitrile¹⁸ (X) with lithium aluminium hydride, was converted to 1-methyl-4-phenyl isoquinoline using the procedure of Govindachari *et al*¹⁹. The identity (TLC, IR, m.p., mixed m.p.) of the synthetic sample with the product obtained from Pictet-Gam's reaction established the structure of the latter.

Mechanism of reaction : In an attempt to understand the mechanism of the reaction, cyclization of the *threo* hydroxy amide (VII) was planned. The *threo* amine XI^{20,21} on acetylation furnished a diacetate, whose cyclodehydration furnished a product identical with that (VI) obtained from the *erythro* compound (VII). As no 1-methyl-3-phenyl isoquinoline could be detected (TLC) a concerted mechanism for the rearrangement can be ruled out.

It may be pointed out that when dehydration of the *erythro* amide (VII) was carried out using Grignard²² reagent and the crude product was treated with PPA-POCl₃ mixture an essentially pure (TLC) product was obtained. The solid m.p. 48° obtained on crystallisation was identified (TLC, IR, m.p., mixed m.p.) as 1-methyl-3-phenyl isoquinoline (V). This

*The C-1 proton of Isoquinoline appears at 9.5 δ while the C-3 proton appears at 8.75 δ . The shielding effect observed in the present case represents a cumulative effect of the C-4 phenyl and C₁-methyl groups.

17. G. Berti and P. Corti, *Ann. Chim.*, 1959, **49**, 2110 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1960, **54**, 14934 g.
18. K. Sisido, H. Nozaki, M. Nozaki and K. Okano, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1954, **19**, 1699.
19. T. R. Govindachari, B. R. Pai and U. R. Rao, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1958, **48A**, 111
20. W. D. McPhee and E. S. Enoson Jr., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 624.
21. A. Weissberger and H. Bach., *Ber.*, 1932, **651**, 631.
22. W. Krabbe, E. Polzin and K. Culemeyer, *Ber.*, 1931, **64**, 1095.

led to the conclusion that the rearrangement is acid catalysed and takes place prior to elimination of water.

Extension of the reaction to substituted compounds : The *threo* amine²⁰ (XI, m.p. 126°) was treated with formic acid to afford a compound m.p. 211° whose IR spectrum [bands at 3300 (NH), 1710 (ester), 1660 (amide)] indicated it to be a diformyl derivative (XII). Cyclodehydration with POCl₃ yielded a product whose TLC indicated it to be essentially a single component. Purification by crystallisation afforded stout needles, C₁₅H₁₁N, m.p. 79-80°, picrate m.p. 209°. These properties agree with those of 4-phenyl isoquinoline (XII, m.p. 79-80°, picrate m.p. 209°²³) and differs appreciably from that of 3-phenyl isoquinoline (XIV, m.p. 102-03° picrate)²⁴. These conclusions, agreeing with the observations made in the case of the acetate, are corroborated by the UV (Table 1) and NMR (Table 2) spectra.

Pictet-Gam's reaction of the methylenedioxy amide (XV) has been reported¹⁹ to yield the corresponding 3-phenyl isoquinoline (XVI) m.p. 138°. However, on the basis of the above experiments, it could be anticipated that this compound should be the 4-phenyl isomer (XVII). As the original preparation¹⁹ of the amide involves electrolytic reduction a simpler method had to be adopted for its preparation.

Addition of methanol to the nitrostyrene (XVIII)²⁵ gave the product XIX, which on reduction and acetylation could be elaborated to the amide (XX). The essentially pure compound (TLC), obtained on POCl₃ cyclisation of (XX), on crystallisation, provided colourless needles m.p. 137-38° identical* with that reported by Govindachari and coworkers¹⁹. That this compound was, indeed, not the 3-phenyl isomer (XVI) could be established by direct comparison with a sample of this compound prepared as follows .

Reduction of the nitrostyrene (XVIII) provided the amine, whose acetate (XXI) on Bischler-Napieralski cyclisation³ furnished the corresponding 3, 4 dihydroisoquinoline as an oil characterised as its picrate m p. 207°, similar to that reported earlier³⁰. Dehydrogenation afforded the 3-phenyl isoquinoline (XVI) characterised by its UV (Table 1) and NMR (Table 2) spectra.

*Direct comparison with Prof. Govindachari's sample was not possible as this sample was not available with these workers.

23. G. Berti, *Chem. Abs.*, 1938, **52**, 15536.

24. N. Vinot, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1960, 617.

25. E. Knovanagel and L. Walter, *Ber.*, 1904, **37**, 4502.

26. T. Kametani and K. Otsuki, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1954, **74**, 621

27. J. Read and I. G. M. Campbell, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 2674.

28. G. N. Dorofeenko, E. V. Kuznetsova and S. V. Krivun, *Chem. Abs.*, 1967, **66**, 46287.

29. A. Werssberger and H. Bach, *Ber.*, 1931, **64**, 1095.

30. B. B. Dey and V. S. Ramanathan, *Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1943, **9**, 193.

Once the non-identity of the Pictet-Gam's product (XVII) with the authentic sample of the corresponding 3-phenyl isoquinoline is established, it can be suggested that the Pictet-Gam's product is in fact the 4-phenyl isomer, a contention supported by the UV (Table 1) and PMR (Table 2) spectra.

The next compound chosen was one in which both phenyl rings contained the methylenedioxy group. Cyclodehydration of such an acetate (XXII) of the *erythro* amine (XXIII, m.p. 190-91.5°) has been reported by Kametani and Otsuki²⁶ to yield a syrup from which a picrate m.p. 237-39° could be obtained.

As preparation of the *erythro* amine is cumbersome it was planned to study this reaction on the acetate of the more readily available²⁷ *threo* amine (XXIII, m.p. 159°). Such an acetylation instead provided the diacetate* [(XXIV), IR bands 3280 (NH), 1740 (ester), 1650 (amide)]. Cyclisation of this amide (XXIV) with POCl₃ furnished a product whose TLC (benzene-EtOAc, 9 : 1)-indicated the presence of a major (slower moving) and a minor component. PLC separation afforded both components in pure form.

The faster moving component, obtained as light brown needles, m.p. 167°, picrate m.p. 242°, had properties similar to those (m.p. 167°, picrate m.p. 207°) reported²⁸ for a sample of the 3-aryl isomer (XXV) prepared by an unambiguous route.

The major component m.p. 139° could therefore be anticipated to be the 4-Phenyl isomer (XXVI), this contention was confirmed by the NMR spectrum (Table 2).

It is interesting to note that though the 3, 4 methylenedioxy phenyl is a better migrating group than the phenyl³², the present example is the only one in which the 3-aryl isomer could be isolated though in very low yield. No explanation can be given at present for this behaviour.

EXPERIMENTAL

All m.p. and b.p. are uncorrected. Pet. ether refers to the fraction b.p. 60-80°.

U.V. spectra were taken on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer model 350 in 95% EtOH. IR spectra were recorded as smears (liquids), or Nujol mulls (solids), on a model 221 Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer. All NMR spectra were taken on ~10% soln. in CCl₄ or CDCl₃ (unless stated otherwise) with TMS as internal standard on a Varian A-60 spectrometer. Signals are recorded in δ values relative to TMS as zero.

TLC was carried out on silica gel (containing 15% plaster of paris) on layers of 0.3 mm thickness. Conc. H₂SO₄ was used for the visualization of the spots.

N-Acetyl- α , β diphenyl- β -hydroxy ethylamine (VII): The *erythro* amine²⁹ (XI, m.p. 164°, 5 g) was dissolved in Ac₂O (10 ml) and kept overnight. After addition of Et₂O (50 ml),

**Threo*-hydroxy amines (XI & XXIII) prepared by condensation of aromatic aldehydes with glycine readily furnish the diacyl derivative whereas the stereo isomeric *erythro* hydroxy amines under the same condition furnish only the *N*-acetates.

31. V. K. Bhalla, U. R. Nayak and Sukh Dev, *J. Chromatog.*, 1967, **26**, 54.

32. S. Winstein *et al.*, *J. Amer Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 1113, 1120, 1127, 1140, 1147, 1157.

the crystalline mass was filtered, washed with Et_2O and recrystallised from C_6H_6 . It was obtained as fine needles (5 g) m.p. 199-200° (Lit¹⁰ m.p. 197-98°).

Cyclisation of the amide (VII) : A mixture of PPA [from P_2O_5 (6 g) and H_3PO_4 (4 g)] and POCl_3 (20 ml) was added to a solution of the amide (VII, 2 g) in dry toluene. The reaction mixture was refluxed with stirring till evolution of HCl ceases (~5 hr). The product was poured in water (500 ml), and after separation of layers, the aq. phase was extracted with Et_2O . The aq. layer was made alkaline (NaOH) and exhaustively extracted with Et_2O . The extract was washed (H_2O), dried (K_2CO_3) and solvent flashed off. The residue obtained as a syrup solidified on standing. Crystallisation from pet. ether furnished light brown needles (1 g) m.p. 79-80°, identified by its spectral properties as 1-methyl 4-phenyl isoquinoline (Found : C, 87.36 ; H, 6.16 ; N, 6.31. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}$ requires : C, 87.64 ; H, 5.98 ; N, 6.39%).

Synthesis of the isoquinoline (V) : (a) 1-Methyl-3-phenyl-5, 6, 7, 8-tetrahydroisoquinoline: A mixture of aq. NH_3 and the pyrrilium perchlorate¹⁵ (VIII-2.5 g) was allowed to stand for 16 hr at 0° and then at room temperature (~28°) for 16 hr. The product, after usual work up, gave an oil which on standing furnished needles (1.3 g, 77%) m.p. 80°, picrate m.p. 172-73° (Lit²² picrate m.p. 173°).

(b) 1-Methyl-3-phenyl isoquinoline (V) : The above tetrahydroderivative (5 g) was heated with Pd/C (0.5 g, 30%) at 200° for 6 hr in a current of CO_2 . The cooled reaction mixture was filtered, after addition of ether (100 ml). The dried (Na_2SO_4) filtrate, after solvent removal afforded an oil, shown by TLC to be a mixture of two components.

Chromatography over SiO_2 gel (150 g) yielded in the pet. ether- C_6H_6 (19 : 1) eluate the major component, while the pet. ether- C_6H_6 (1 : 1) eluate contained the unreacted starting material (0.5 g) identified by usual (TLC, IR) methods.

Crystallisation of the major component furnished prisms (2.6 g) m.p. 47-48° (Lit¹⁴ m.p. 48-49°) identified by spectral methods as 1-methyl-3-phenyl isoquinoline (Found : C, 87.76 ; H, 6.13 ; N, 6.28. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}$ requires : C, 87.64 ; H, 5.98 ; N, 6.39%).

Synthesis of the isoquinoline (VI)

(a) 2, 2-Diphenyl-ethylamine (IX) : A solution of AlCl_3 (13.3 g) in ether (150 ml) was added rapidly to a stirred solution of LiAlH_4 (3.8 g) in ether (100 ml). Five min. after completion of AlCl_3 addition, a soln. of diphenyl acetonitrile¹⁸ (X, 19.3 g) in ether (200 ml) was added to the well stirred mixture. One hour after addition, excess hydride was decomposed with water and dil. H_2SO_4 (6 N, 140 ml). Usual work up yielded a neutral (0.1 g) and a basic component (19 g). Distillation of the basic component furnished the amine (IX, 17 g, 165°/2 mm) m.p. 44-45°.

(b) 1-Methyl-4-phenyl isoquinoline (VI) : The amine (IX, 2 g) was acetylated and cyclised according to the procedure of Dey and Ramanathan³⁰ to furnish the dihydroisoquinoline (1.5 g) as an oil, picrate m.p. 170° (Lit. m.p. 170°).

A soln. of this dihydroisoquinoline (1 g) in *p*-cymens (10 ml) was refluxed for 6 hr. with Raney Nickel (1 ml). The cooled reaction mixture was filtered and extracted with dil. HCl:

The aq. phase was made alkaline and worked up in the usual way to provide a brown solid (0.8 g) which furnished needles m.p. 79-80° (Lit.¹⁹ m.p. 80°) from pet-ether, picrate m.p. 225-26° (Lit. m.p. 226°). (Found : C, 87.26 ; H, 6.09 ; N, 6.74 C₁₆H₁₃N requires : C, 87.64 ; H, 5.98, N, 6.39%). This compound, identified by spectral means as VI, was identical (TLC, IR, m.p., mixed m.p.) with the product obtained from Pictet-Gam's reaction on the amide (VII).

Diacetate of threo amine (XI) . The *threo* amine²⁰ (XI, m.p. 126°, 2 g) after usual acetylation gave colourless needles (2 g) m.p. 143-44° (Lit.²¹ m.p. 143-44°) from EtOH (Found : C, 72.93 ; H, 6.38 ; N, 4.69 C₁₈H₁₉NO₃ requires : C, 72.71 ; H, 6.44 ; N, 4.71%).

Cyclisation of the above amide : Cyclisation of this amide (2 g) as described for the *erythro* amide (VII) gave only 1-methyl-4-phenyl isoquinoline (0.9 g) identified by usual methods (IR, TLC, m.p.). No 1-methyl-3-phenyl isoquinoline could be detected (TLC) in the crude reaction product.

N-acetyl- α , β -diphenyl-vinyl amine : A soln. of the Grignard reagent [prepared from Mg (0.15 g) and C₂H₅Br (0.5 g)] in ether (20 ml) is added to the amide (VII, 0.3 g) suspended in ether (15 ml). The reaction is stirred for 15 min. after addition is complete. Removal of ether under anhydrous conditions yielded a residue which was slowly heated for 30 min. to 170-75° at which temp. it was maintained for 45 min. After cooling, the product was worked up as usual, to furnish a gum (0.15 g).

This gum on purification by IDCC³¹ on SiO₂ using C₆H₆-EtOAc (1 : 1) furnished two pure fractions—one (50 mg) identified (TLC, IR, m.p.) as the starting material and the other an oil (90 mg) which was directly used further.

Cyclisation of the above vinyl amide : Treatment of the above oil with PPA-POCl₃ as described before afforded a product (47 mg) m.p. 47-48° identified by direct comparison (IR, TLC, m.p.) as 1-methyl-3 phenyl isoquinoline

Threo- O, N-Diformyl- α , β diphenyl- β hydroxy ethyl amine (XII) : The *threo* amine²⁰ (XI, m.p. 126°, 1 g) was refluxed with formic acid (25 ml) and fused NaOAc (10 g) for 10 hr. and poured into crushed ice (200 g). After a day the solid which separated (0.9 g) was collected and crystallised from C₆H₆ as needles m.p. 211°. (Found : C, 70.97 ; H, 5.64 ; N, 5.11. C₁₆H₁₅NO₃ requires : C, 71.36 ; H, 5.61 ; N, 5.20%).

Cyclisation of the amide (XII) : The amide (XII, 0.5 g) was cyclised using the standard procedure. The product (0.3 g essentially pure by TLC) on crystallisation afforded stout yellow needles m.p. 79-80°, picrate m.p. 208° (Lit.²³ m.p. 79-80°, picrate m.p. 209°) identified as XIII from its spectral properties. (Found : C, 87.35 ; H, 5.31 ; N, 6.59. C₁₅H₁₁N requires : C, 87.77 ; H, 5.40 ; N, 6.82%).

Preparation of amide (XV) : (a) α -Phenyl- β (3, 4 methylenedioxy phenyl)- β -methoxy nitro ethane (XIX).

A methanolic soln. (2N, 4 ml) of sodium methoxide was added to a fine suspension (prepared by rapid cooling, to room temp., of a hot soln) of the nitrostyrene³⁵ (XVII, 2 g) in anhydrous methanol (150 ml). After shaking for 5 min. the reaction product was

quenched by acidification with glacial AcOH (1 ml). The solid residue obtained after evaporation (under *vacuo*) was diluted with water (50 ml) and extracted with ether. Evaporation of the dried (Na_2SO_4) ethereal soln. left a residue which was obtained as needles (2 g) m.p. 147° from MeOH. (Found : C, 63.81 ; H, 4.98 ; N, 4.37. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_3$ requires : C, 63.78 ; H, 5.02 ; N, 4.65%).

(b) *N*-acetyl- α -phenyl- β -(3, 4 methylenedioxy phenyl)- β -methoxy-ethyl amine (XX) : A soln. of the nitro compound (XIX, 1.5 g) in dry THF (50 ml) was reduced using LiAlH_4 (0.7 g) in THF (25 ml). Usual work up gave the saturated amine as an oil, the acetate of which was obtained as needles (1 g) m.p. $167-68^\circ$ from C_6H_6 . IR spectrum : 3300 (NH), 1650 (amide) and 1150 cm^{-1} (ether). (Found : C, 68.79 ; H, 5.98 ; N, 4.53. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}_4$ requires : C, 69.00 ; H, 6.11 ; N, 4.47%).

Cyclisation of the amide (XX) : A soln. of the amide (XX, 0.5 g) in dry toluene (5 ml) was refluxed with POCl_3 (2 ml) for 6 hrs. Usual work up gave the crude product (TLC, single spot) which afforded needles (0.25 g) m.p. $137-38^\circ$ (Lit¹⁹ m.p. 138°) from pet. ether; and was found from its spectral properties as the rearranged isoquinoline (XVII). (Found : C, 77.47 ; H, 5.07 ; N, 5.71. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_2$ requires : C, 77.55 ; H, 4.98 ; N, 5.32%.)

1-Methyl-3-phenyl-6, 7 methylenedioxy isoquinoline (XVI) : The dihydroisoquinoline³⁰ (dihydro XVI, 0.5 g) dissolved in *p*-cymene was dehydrogenated as before using Raney-nickel to yield needles m.p. $150-51^\circ$ identified as the 1-methyl-3-aryl isoquinoline (XVI) by its spectral properties. (Found : C, 77.92 ; H, 5.11 ; N, 5.23. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_2$ requires : C, 77.55 ; H, 4.98, N, 5.32%).

O, *N*-Diacetyl- α , β -di-(3, 4-methylenedioxy-phenyl)- β -hydroxy ethylamine (XXIV) : The *threo* amine²⁷ (XXIII, m.p. 159° , 1 g) furnished on acetylation a product (1.05 g) m.p. $179-80^\circ$ identified as the diacetate. (Found : C, 62.12 ; H, 4.64 ; N, 3.95. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}_7$ requires : C, 62.33 ; H, 4.97 ; N, 3.63%).

Cyclisation of XXIV : The amide (XXIV, 1 g) was cyclised using POCl_3 (vide supra) to furnish a product (0.4 g) which contained a major and a minor (faster moving) component (TLC). The two products were separated by PLC using SiO_2 layer of 1 mm thickness and C_6H_6 -EtOAc (1 : 1) as the solvent system.

The minor component gave crystals from EtOH m.p. 167° , picrate m.p. 242° (d) (Lit²⁸ m.p. 167°) (Found : C, 54.16 ; H, 2.78 ; N, 10.93%. The picrate $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{O}_{11}$ requires : C, 53.73 ; H, 3.01 ; N, 10.44%).

The major component was obtained as buff coloured needles m.p. 139° from MeOH, and was identified as the isoquinoline (XXVI) from its spectral properties. (Found : C, 70.62 ; H, 4.24 ; N, 4.37. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_4$ requires : C, 70.35 ; H, 4.26 ; N, 4.56%).

